

Investigation of the Emission of Ionic Species

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Abstract:

Ionization rate coefficients, recombination rate coefficients, electron impact excitation coefficients and fractional abundances of the different ionic species of the elements have been investigated. We have computed the radiative as well as dielectronic recombination and total recombination rate coefficients of Cu II, Cu III and Cu IV as a function of electron temperature. We obtained the fractional abundances of the elements like Cu, Zn, Li, Na, K, and Mg as a function of electron temperature. The computations show that the fractional abundance of the species changes as the electron temperature is varied. With the help of energy level diagrams of the elements we found the color of emission of the species from allowed and resonant transitions.

Keywords: Radiative, Dielectronic, Fractional Abundances, Ionic species, Electron temperature.

Introduction:

In the interface of solid and liquid the discharge takes place when the dc voltage is applied across solid and liquid interfaced electrodes. The discharge column consists of electrons and the ions of metallic elements contained in the electrolytic solutions with different charges. The ions and electrons undergo collisions among themselves and with walls of the discharge column. M.H.Elghazaly et al. (2007) have studied [1], the most important rate coefficients for electron collisions in noble gases, electron-neutral ionization and electron impact excitation [1]. They studied electron-neutral ionization besides electron impact excitation of some states of the argon and helium atom in DC glow discharge plasma. Electron properties as well as the calculated rate coefficients (ionization and excitation) were studied as a function of the axial distance from the cathode while the discharge operating parameters of voltage and pressure were varied [1]. S W Simpson et al. (1990) have studied ionization and recombination rates in argon plasmas [2]. They presented approximate model for treating multi-step ionization and recombination in inert gas plasmas [2].

The discharge consists of a mixture of atoms, electrons and ions of different charges. The processes of ionization results in increasing density of ions and electrons in the discharge column. When the positive ion in the discharge column comes in contact with an electron may try to capture an electron and recombine to form an ion of lower charge. The probability with which an electron is captured depends upon the velocity of an electron relative to the ion. The recombination processes are divided into two categories depending on the initial states such as i) Radiative recombination and ii) Dielectronic recombination. The total recombination rate of an ion is the sum of these two rate

coefficients With this background a little attempt has been made to investigate emission of the ionic species. For this we obtained the ionization rate coefficients, recombination rate coefficients, electron impact coefficients and fractional abundances of the different ionic species of the elements.

Mathematical Formulation:

Radiative Recombination Rate

The theory proposed by Seaton [3, 4] for the calculation of ionization rate as well as the recombination rate for the experimental conditions in solar corona helps in obtaining the recombination rate coefficient also. In the theory the recombination rate was calculated using the equation

$$\alpha_{Z+1} = 1.003 \times 10^{-11} \frac{Z^2}{T_e^{1/2}} \sigma \frac{I_Z}{KT_e} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

Where, z - is the charge

T_e - is the electron temperature

σ - is the slowly varying function of I_Z/KT_e .

The value of σ have been tabulated by Seaton [3]. The value of electron density and the electron temperature in solar corona are smaller than those in the laser discharge tubes operating at optimum conditions. Hence Seaton's theory may not be used for the calculation of recombination rate coefficients. The theory had to be modified for the computations of the recombination rates in plasma where the electron temperature is of the order of few electron volts and the electron density is of the order of 10^{12} to 10^{13} cm^{-3} C Breton et al [5] suggested the formula for the calculation of recombination rate in plasma having above range of parameter values and it is expressed as

$$\alpha_{rz} = 2.6 \times 10^{-14} (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2) \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

Where,

α_1 and α_2 for Maxwellian distribution of electron density are given as

$$\alpha_1 = Z^2 \left(\frac{I_H}{T_e} \right)^{1/2} \frac{\mu}{n^3} \left(\frac{I_{Z-1}}{T_e} \right) e^{I_{Z-1}/T_e} \cdot E_1 \left(\frac{I_{Z-1}}{T_e} \right) \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

and

$$\alpha_2 = \sum_{\nu=1} \left(\frac{2}{(n+\nu)^3} \cdot Z^4 \right) \left(\frac{I_H}{T_e} \right)^{3/2} \exp \left(\frac{Z^2 I_H}{(n+\nu)^2 T_e} \right) E_1 \left(\frac{Z^2 I_H}{(n+\nu)^2 T_e} \right) \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

where

I_H is ionization potential of hydrogen i.e. 13.6 eV,
 n is principle quantum number,
 I_{z-1} is ionization potential of ion after recombination,
 μ is the number of empty places in the valence shell,
 $E_1(x)$ is the exponential integral function.

The function $E(x)$ is known as an exponential integral function and it is expressed in the form

$$E_1(\infty) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-x}}{x} dx$$

This function plays vital role in the calculations of the ionization rate coefficients. The function arises through the velocity distribution of the electrons in the discharge. The electrons in the discharge have Maxwellian velocity distribution. The lower limit of the integral depends upon the ionization potential in case of the calculation of the ionization rate coefficient and the recombination rate coefficient and it depends upon height of the energy level from ground state in case of the calculation of the electron impact excitation rate coefficient.

Dielectronic Recombination Rate

The dielectronic recombination rates of the ions existing in plasma have been investigated in details [6-8]. The electron density in plasma has some influence on the radiative recombination rate. If the influence of electron density is neglected, the dielectronic recombination rate coefficient of an ion with charge Z can be expressed as

$$\alpha_{dz} = \frac{1}{T_e^{3/2}} B_{(z)} \sum_j A_{(z,j)} \exp \left(- \frac{E_{zj}}{T_e} \right) \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

The summation extends over all the resonance levels j of the recombining ions of charge Z so that the total recombination rate is obtained.

Where E_{zj} is total energy of the resonance transition j , and the terms $B(z)$, $A(z,j)$ are obtained as

$$B_{(z)} = 6.5 \times 10^{-10} Z^{1/2} (Z+1)^2 / (Z^2 + 13.4)^{1/2}$$

and

$$A_{(z,j)} = \frac{f_{zj} (E_{zj})^{1/2}}{1 + 0.105 \chi_{zj} + 0.015 \chi_{zj}^2}$$

Where f_{zj} is the absorption oscillator strength of the resonant transition j of ion z and the factor χ_{zj} is given by

$$\chi_{zj} = \left(\frac{E_{zj}}{(Z+1)} \right) \cdot I_H$$

Fractional Abundances

The glow discharge consists of the electrons and the ions with different charges. The collisions between the atoms, ions of different charges and electrons result in ionization. At the same time the ions may capture the electrons and result in formation of ions of lower charge. The ionization and recombination processes compete each other so that the ionization rate and recombination rates reach; each to a certain value and the equilibrium is attained. As long as the electron temperature is not changed the equilibrium remains in a particular state. A change in electron temperature results in changing the densities of ions and electrons. Thus the densities of ions and electrons are completely dictated by the electron temperature. The discharge emission depends upon the fraction of the total density of a species remaining in a particular ionized state, the electron density and the electron temperature. "The amount of the fraction of the total density of a species remaining in a particular ionized state is called as fractional abundance of that ion". The gaseous discharge has not yet been studied from the point of view to observe the fractional abundances of different ions in the discharges. In fact the relative densities of the neon atoms and ions have been measured by few experiments [9,10]. In the He-Ne laser discharge [11] the radial profiles of the spectral emission have been studied and interpreted in different ways but the results were not explained by considering the idea of fractional abundances. The concepts of fractional abundances have been widely used in order to explain the experimental results in Tokmak plasma discharge. Mathematically it may be expressed as [5,12]

$$F_{z'} = \frac{N_{z'}}{\sum_z N_z} \quad (1)$$

Where

$F_{z'}$ is the fractional abundances of the ion with charge z'

$N_{z'}$ is the density of ion with charge z'

and the sum runs over all possible ionized state. The fractional abundances of a particular species can be evaluated by using the steady state equation

$$\begin{aligned} N_e N_z S_z &= N_e N_{z+1} \alpha_{z+1} \\ N_z S_z &= N_{z+1} \alpha_{z+1} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where

N_e is the electron density

S_z is the ionization rate coefficient of the ion of charge Z

α_{z+1} is the recombination rate coefficient of the ion of charge $Z+1$

N_z, N_{z+1} are the densities of the ions with charge Z and $Z+1$ respectively

Equation (1) can be written as
$$\frac{N_{z+1}}{N_z} = \frac{S_z}{\alpha_{z+1}}$$

i.e. N_{z+1}/N_z can be evaluated in terms of S_z and α_{z+1}

The values of S_z and α_{z+1} are fully determined by electron temperature and hence the fractional abundance and density of any ion in the discharge depends only on the electron temperature. The fractional abundances of a particular species can be evaluated by using equation (1).

Result and Discussion

We have computed the radiative recombination rate coefficient as well as dielectronic recombination rate coefficient of CuII, CuIII and CuIV in the discharge as a function of electron temperature from 0 through 10 eV. The total recombination rate coefficients are then obtained by adding the corresponding values of above two recombination rate coefficients. The radiative and dielectronic recombination rate coefficients for CuII, CuIII and CuIV are plotted as a function of electron temperature in figure 1 and the total recombination rate coefficients for these species are plotted as a function of electron temperature in figure 2. The curves in these figures clearly show that at low electron temperature the radiative recombination rate coefficient is of the order of $(10^{-13}-10^{-12}) \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$. When the electron temperature is near to zero the electron moves slowly in the plasma. The ions in plasma can very easily capture the slow moving electrons and recombine. Thus there is more probability of radiative recombination at electron temperature near zero. As the temperature increases the electrons move faster and it becomes difficult for an ion to capture the electron and therefore the radiative recombination rate coefficient decreases. At low

electron temperature the dielectronic recombination is low as the rate of excitation of the resonant states of the ion is low. The increase of electron temperature increases the excitation rate of the resonant states and hence increasing the dielectronic recombination rate. It is found that the dielectronic recombination rate tends to saturate for electron temperature above 4 eV.

At low electron temperature the entire contribution to the total recombination rate is of the radiative recombination process. As the electron temperature is increased to about 1 eV the total recombination rate coefficient decreases and reaches a minimum value. As the electron temperature is further increased the total recombination rate increases. This is because of the increase in the dielectronic recombination rate coefficients. This increase continues and starts saturating at the electron temperature of about 2eV and becomes almost saturated at electron temperature of 4eV.

When we study the glow discharges of various elements we come to the conclusion that monochromatic light at various wavelengths can be generated using glow discharge.. Few species shows change in color of the glow when the discharge current was increased. In order to investigate the optimum parameters for getting good monochromatic sources applied we obtained the fractional abundances of the species.

The change in color of the glow can also be explained by the theory of fractional abundances. We obtained electron impact excitation rate coefficients, recombination rate coefficients and fractional abundances of the elements like Li,Na,Mg,K,Ni,Cu,Zn,Se,Zr,Cd,Fe and Ti as a function of electron temperature. The few results are displayed in the figures 3 to 8. The results showed that at electron temperature very near to zero the entire species is in neutral form. As the electron temperature is increased the neutral atoms are converted into singly ionized species. Further increase in electron temperature converts singly ionized species into doubly ionized species. This implies that in order to get highly ionized species the electron temperature in the plasma column should be increased.

We draw energy level diagram of the elements and found the color of emission of the species from allowed and resonant transitions. In case of few glow discharges the change in color was observed when the discharge current is increased. In order to investigate the change in color we obtained the difference in the ionization potential of neutral species and singly ionized species and tabulate in the table 1. The table clearly shows that when the difference in ionization potential is low the change in color of glow discharge obtained with more probability. The displays of fractional abundances

also shows that elements in which change of color is observed the difference in the electron temperature for the peak of electron temperature for neutral species and for singly ionized species is very small. If the difference in ionization potential is small slight change in discharge current give rise to change in electron temperature, which converts the neutral species into singly ionized species.

Conclusion:

The keen observation of the displays of fractional abundances show that singly ionized elements (alkali metals and alkaline earth metals) may play very important role in the discharges. The

singly ionized species show its appearance over very wide range of electron temperature. Further doubly ionized Magnesium also shows its appearance over very wide range of electron temperature. The results related to fractional abundances also show that the species like Li II, Na II, K II and Mg III may play the role of buffer gas [13] in case of shorter wavelength Laser designs. The design of X-ray Laser can get some ideas about the operation of the Laser and operating temperature of discharge.

The species like Li II, Na II, K II and Mg III may play very important role in the penning ionization [14] process in the glow discharge.

Figure 1: Radioactive Recombination rate coefficients AR1, AR2, AR3 and Dielectric Recombination Rate Coefficients AD1, AD2, AD3 of CuI, CuII and CuIV as a Function of Electron Temperature

Figure 2: Total Recombination Rate Coefficients AT1, AT2, AT3 of CuI, CuII, CuIV as a function of Electron Temperature

Figure 3: Fractional Abundance of CuI, CuII, CuIII and CuIV as a function of Electron Temperature

Figure 4: Fractional Abundance Of ZnI, ZnII, ZnIII & ZnIV as a function of Electron Temperature

Table 1: Investigation of Change in color

Sr.No.	Element	I.P.I eV	I.P.II eV	I.P.II - I.P.I eV	Colour change
1	Na	5.138	47.29	42.152	No
2	K	4.339	31.81	27.471	No
3	Li	5.39	75.6193	70.2293	No
4	Pb	7.415	15.028	7.613	Yes
5	Mg	7.644	15.03	7.386	Yes
6	Cu	7.724	20.29	12.566	Yes
7	Ag	7.574	21.48	13.906	Yes
8	Ca	6.111	11.87	5.759	Yes
9	Sr	5.692	11.027	5.335	Yes
10	Zn	9.39	17.96	8.57	Yes
11	Se	9.75	21.5	11.75	Yes
12	Zr	6.95	14.03	7.08	Yes
13	Ni	7.633	18.15	10.517	Yes
14	Bi	7.287	16.68	9.393	Yes
15	Fe	7.9	16.18	8.28	Yes
16	Ba	5.21	10.001	4.791	Yes
17	Cd	8.99	16.904	7.914	Yes
18	Al	5.984	18.823	12.839	Yes
19	Ti	6.83	13.63	6.8	Yes
20	Co	7.86	17.05	9.19	Yes

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